

REQUIREMENTS FOR TEACHERS IN TODAY'S INNOVATIVE ERA**Durnazarova Dilyafuz Daurxan qizi**

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Abstract. *This study provides information on modern methods of developing teachers' professional skills based on the conditions of the current state of modern education based on intonational pedagogical approaches. It also provides information on the importance of educational methods in improving teachers' professional potential and pedagogical skills.*

Keywords: *Higher education, teacher, pedagogical skills, professional potential, modern education, innovative pedagogical methods.*

BUGUNGI KUNDAGI INNOVATSION ZAMONDA O'QITUVCHIGA QO'YILGAN TALABLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda hozirgi kunga kelib zamonaviy ta'limda innotasion pedagogik yondashuvlarga asoslangan sharoitlardan kelib chiqqan holda o'qituvchining kasbiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning zamonaviy metodikasi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, o'qituvchilarning kasbiy salohiyati va pedagogik mahoratini oshirishda ta'lim metodlarining ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Oliy ta'lim, o'qituvchi, pedagogik mahorat, kasbiy salohiyat, zamonaviy ta'lim, innovatsion pedagogik metodlar.*

Introduction

The professional formation of a teacher begins in the process of receiving professional education at a higher educational institution. The curricula and subject programs of pedagogical universities provide for the teaching of the secrets of this profession to future teachers, imparting scientific knowledge, providing information about the teaching profession, and developing skills. Seminars, practical and laboratory classes in subjects during the educational process allow not only to consolidate theoretical knowledge and turn them into skills, but also to apply them in practical work. Such classes instill a sense of confidence that the chosen profession is the right one. The pedagogical community at school plays a major role in the professional formation of a teacher after graduation. One of the main tasks of the school management is to assign experienced teachers to young teachers, observe their lessons, and involve them in methodological work. As the teacher gradually masters his profession, he also promotes pedagogical knowledge among parents. In this way, his professional formation also improves. It depends on the young teacher himself whether he can master the teaching profession and pedagogical skills, enter the school teaching team and find his place in it. Not turning away from the help of the team, not losing heart when facing difficulties, being able to see his mistakes and try to eliminate them, indicates his formation as a teacher. At the same time, the professional formation of a teacher is inextricably linked to self-education, constant

work on himself and timely improvement of his qualifications. All these are an integral part of professional qualities. The theoretical and methodological arming of the education system aimed at the comprehensive development of the personality is today defined as the main goal of pedagogical science. Successfully fulfilling the high, but honorable tasks described above requires high professional skills, knowledge and a broad outlook from each pedagogical worker. Pedagogical skill is the highest example of a teacher's creativity, which is formed over the years. Its acquisition of high skill is an extremely complex process and is one of the most pressing problems of pedagogical science. Along with the many qualities inherent in the teaching profession, the acquisition of pedagogical skill is of great importance. Only a teacher with high pedagogical skill can be competent and talented in his profession. To work successfully, every teacher must have high pedagogical skill and a broad outlook. Only then will he achieve great results with little effort, and creativity will always be his companion. Only a person capable of pedagogical work and talented can have pedagogical skill. For pedagogical activity to be effective, a teacher must have a deep knowledge of his subject, have an understanding of related subjects, be able to explain the educational material in a way that is understandable to students, arouse interest in independent active thinking in students, take into account the level of knowledge, maturity and mentality of students, be able to imagine what they know and what they do not know yet. A capable, experienced teacher can put himself in the shoes of a student, he works on the basis that what is clear and understandable to adults may be difficult and abstract for students. Therefore, he thinks out and plans the character and form of the presentation separately. The teacher must conduct psychological observations related to the ability to penetrate the student's inner world, to understand the student's personality and his temporary mental states very well. Such a teacher quickly understands even the most subtle changes in the student's psyche. Speech in a teacher is the ability to clearly and clearly express his thoughts and feelings. This is very important for the teaching profession. The teacher's speech should be clear, lively, figurative, bright in pronunciation, expressive, emotional, and should not contain stylistic, grammatical, or phonetic defects. The teacher's reputation is to have a direct emotional and volitional impact on students and to gain reputation on this basis. Reputation is gained not only on this basis, but also on the basis of the teacher's good knowledge of the subject, kindness, gentleness, etc. It also depends on feeling responsible for educating and nurturing students, believing that one is right, and being able to convey this belief to students. The qualities inherent in the teaching profession, that is, high pedagogical skills, are not formed in him at once. It develops on the basis of constant work on oneself, research and skills. The acquisition of high professional skills by a teacher is carried out directly through the system of continuous education. Advanced training, which occupies a key place in the system of continuous education, allows for the analysis of student activity and provides him with promising directions. The current era requires a teacher to correctly understand the requirements of advanced pedagogical technologies of teaching, to be proactive, to be aware of innovations in his subject and to be able to implement them in his lessons. The education system in our country reveals special requirements and special pedagogical relations for a fair and effective educational process. This process is fundamentally different in content and essence from the previous one. This requires the cooperation of students, teachers, families, and communities in the field of education towards one goal, namely, mastering the requirements of the state educational standard and achieving results that exceed its standards. The task of

educating socially active, highly spiritual youth who are creative, independent thinkers, and who are able to apply advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational process, increase the effectiveness of education, and put scientific achievements into practice is of great importance. In order to provide young people with knowledge that meets the requirements of the times, a teacher must first be armed with such knowledge himself. After all, the basis of success in the system is determined by the quality of the teaching process organized in schools. Providing students with sufficient knowledge during school hours, improving their life skills and forming their qualifications depends on the professional skills of the teacher. By teaching students to express their own opinions, choose their own direction and prove their views, and defend them when necessary, the result of the educational content is that young people are able to form skills to prepare for an independent life. The development of communicative skills through personalized educational technologies is taken into account in the editorial process, where students act as the main subject. In this process, they strive to demonstrate communicative activity to their peers, activate communicative skills, and master a culture of interpersonal communication. At the same time, students independently seek ways to achieve these goals. Our observations have shown that education is the main driving force in developing students' communicative skills through personalized learning technologies, and it is necessary to arm it with pedagogical theory to prepare it for this process. It became clear that there is a need to develop relevant scientific and methodological recommendations in order to identify the pedagogical conditions for developing students' communicative skills through personalized learning technologies, collect, classify existing approaches, concepts, views, and teachings in this area, and introduce them into teaching activities.

Studies conducted in the world and in our republic on the development of students' communicative skills through educational technologies introduced to teachers show that today, it is necessary to organize teacher-student cooperation, manage the pedagogical process, study irregular phenomena in the pedagogical process, and study the issues of new interpretations of the world within the framework of synergy. There is a need to organize the content of education based on European international standards and to study issues aimed at developing the general, specific, professional and personal competence of specialists.

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